

TOXICITY OF BOTANICALS AND SYNTHETIC INSECTICIDES AGAINST COTTON BOLLWORMS UNDER DIFFERENT IRRIGATION REGIMES

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Abstract

Cotton, *Gossypium hirsutum*, is one of the most important cash crops in Pakistan. Insect pests are major limiting factor in crop production. The present research work was carried out to evaluate the toxic potentials of botanicals and synthetic insecticides against American bollworm, *Helicoverpa armigera*, Pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiellaa* and Spotted bollworm, *Earias insulana*. Toxicity bioassays were conducted using plant oils (Neem oil, *Jatropha* oil, Castor-bean oil and G1-garlic oil) at 10, 20 and 30% concentrations against all three insect species. In case of infested bolls per plant by *H. armigera* infestation, the highest number of infested cotton bolls (averaging 2.01 per plant) was observed in BS-15 cotton variety planted with *Jatropha* oil under single lateral at 30 cm spacing, whereas the lowest count (averaging 0.49 per plant) was found with Profenofos+Cypermethrin under single lateral at 40 cm within the same cotton genotype. However, fewer infested bolls were noted in the CKC-3 cotton variety. For *E. insulana* infestation, the greatest number of infested cotton bolls (averaging 3.21 per plant) was seen in BS-15 cotton with garlic oil under double lateral at 30 cm spacing, while the lowest count (averaging 0.54 per plant) occurred with Lamdacyhalothrin under single lateral at 40 cm. In CKC-3 cotton, the highest infestation counts (averaging 2.92 per plant) were observed with garlic oil under double lateral at 30 cm spacing, and the lowest (averaging 0.39 per plant) with Lamdacyhalothrin under single lateral at 40 cm. *P. gossypiella* infestation resulted in the maximum number of infested cotton bolls (averaging 3.23 per plant) in BS-15 cotton with garlic oil under double lateral at 40 cm spacing, while the minimum (averaging 0.58 per plant) was recorded with Profenofos+Cypermethrin under single lateral at 40 cm. In CKC-3 cotton, the highest infestation counts (averaging 2.92 per plant) were noted with garlic oil under double lateral at 30 cm spacing, and the lowest (averaging 0.37 per plant) with Profenofos+Cypermethrin under single lateral at 40 cm. Regarding crop water productivity was highest (0.19 kgm⁻³) in case of CKC-3 under drip irrigation plot compared with corresponding flood irrigated plot. Hence, integrated

use of botanicals and the synthetic insecticides could be useful for effective control of the three cotton bollworms leading to maximization of the cotton yield.

INTRODUCTION

Cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum*) is among the high valued crops throughout the world (Yang *et al.*, 2023). It is a fibre crop and mainly used in textile industry (Zhang *et al.*, 2023). Pakistan is the fifth largest cotton producer globally (Sohail *et al.*, 2023). In Pakistan, 60 percent of the produced cotton is being export as textile merchandises. It represents around 2.4 percent of the value contributed in agriculture and 0.6 percent of Pakistan's GDP. Cotton is being grown on 1,937 thousand hectares with yield of 8.329 million bales (Government of Pakistan, 2020). Over the past few decades, these are reports of decrease of cotton fibre due to the use of chemically synthesized fibres (Rauf *et al.*, 2019). Moreover, the decline is also accredited to climatic changes and pest outbreaks (Dilek *et al.*, 2022).

Cotton crop is being attack by a number of sucking insect pests and bollworms. Among them, American bollworm, *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hubner) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) is considered as one of the main insect pests of many agricultural crops including fiber crops (Riaz *et al.*, 2021). This pest causes damage to crops estimated at greater than USD 2 billion annually in Asia, Europe, Africa, and Australasia (Tay *et al.*, 2013). The insect is polyphagous and used to feed on a variety of agricultural crops; around two hundred crops and capable to survive in varied climatic conditions (Chen *et al.*, 2020). Among the crops attacked by *H. armigera*, cotton, fodders, tobacco and oil seed crops of prime importance (Gu *et al.*, 2018; Palagacheva and Sevo, 2021). *H. armigera* is a serious pest because of its polyphagy, high fecundity (Noor-ul-Ane *et al.*, 2018), greater movement (Yang *et al.*, 2022) and resistance to synthetic entomocidal chemicals (Tossou *et al.*, 2019). Larvae stage of *H. armigera* are voracious feeder and under high infestation cause significant yield losses in cotton crop. Larvae of the insect pests primarily attack the cotton crop resulting in massive losses. As the larvae of this insect pest hide in fruits, bolls, or pods, so chemical sprays could

not control the pest effectively (Ravi *et al.*, 2020). So, regular monitoring for timely detection of the insect population and application of appropriate insecticide is of prime importance for its control (Rajput *et al.* 2017; Safna *et al.*, 2018). Another important bollworm of cotton is the Pink Bollworm (PBW), *Pectinophora gossypiella*. In Pakistan, this insect has attained a rank of forthcoming epidemic for cotton. Larvae of this insect are pink-colored, monophagous and diapause in double seed (Shahid *et al.*, 2021). Earlier the application of pesticides and cultivation of cotton hybrids usually Bt crops, this insect pest hugely abridged the crop yield in Pakistan (Ghramh *et al.*, 2022). But current farmer's field situation revealed the stern PBW attack might be due to unequal spells of rain during monsoon season and upsurge in climate temperature (Shuli *et al.*, 2018). Spotted bollworm *Earias vittella* (Lepidoptera: Nolidae) is a polyphagous pest with significant impact on the economy that mostly affects cotton. Larvae of this insect may completely kill cotton crop buds and bolls, making it a truly serious pest (Sandal *et al.*, 2023).

Bio-derived insecticides being natural and eco-friendly are getting importance these days to be applied for the control filed as stored commodities insect pests (Kobenan *et al.*, 2018; Lyubenova *et al.*, 2023). The insecticides have the capability of insect control without harming the quality of the produce (Kumar *et al.*, 2021). Several studies described plant derived materials having insecticidal properties and hence having sufficient potential to be practiced against numerous kinds of insect pests. Neem extract is the most usually practiced natural entomotoxic material. Azadirachtin is the active compound extracted from different parts of the neem plant, like seeds and leaves. Azadirachtin is one of the plant products for efficient management of the lepidopteron and many other insect pests (Fernandes *et al.*, 2019). Oil of *Jatropha curcas* was

found to be toxic against *H. armigera* (Valdez-Ramirez *et al.*, 2023). In a toxicity bioassay, castor oil and garlic oil resulted in mortality of against *H. armigera* (Balmala *et al.*, 2023). Among the synthetic insecticides, Pyrethroids like Lamda-cyhalothrin, has been used to control *H. armigera* (Alemu *et al.*, 2022) and *P. gossypiella* (Radwan *et al.*, 2018). Organophosphorus insecticides have shown remarkable toxicity against a variety of chewing insects of crops (Aly *et al.*, 2023). Amides group found effective against *Earias insulana* (Mangrio *et al.*, 2023).

Use of all the insect pest management tactics in an integrated way has attained huge importance in past few years. The philosophy of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) programme is intellectual use of all the possible insect control techniques in a compatible manner to minimize the cost of crop protection (Baker *et al.*, 2020). The purpose of this programme is to keep the insect pest number below economic threshold level. Though bio-derived chemicals are slow-release insecticides compared to synthetic pesticides yet have been found effective against many lepidopteran insect pests (Liu *et al.*, 2021) However, in Pakistan, there are very a smaller number of listed bio-derived

insecticides for control of bollworms. Therefore, the proposed research trial was focused on assessing the relative effectiveness of some bio-derived insecticides together with the synthetic insecticides against *H. armigera*, *E. insulana* and *P. gossypiella*.

Materials and Methods

Location of study area

The research trials were conducted at Water Management Research Farm Renala Khurd, Okara in 2023.

Experimental Layout

The experimental layout was set up in a randomized complete block design (RCBD). The experiment was comprised of two cotton varieties; BS-15 and CKC-3, were sown and irrigations were done through surface/flood and drip irrigation arrangements. Row to row was 120 cm, and plant to plant was 30 and 40 cm apart. The experimental area was divided into three blocks (replicates) each having an area of 671 m². Treatments and control were replicated (blocks) in thrice. All the other agronomic practices were followed for optimal growth of the crop.

Table 1 Treatments description

Sr. No	Trade name	Active ingredient	Dose rate per acre
1	Curacron	Pofenophos	350 ml
2	Karate	Lamda-cyhalothrin	330 ml
3	Proclaim	Emamectin-Benzoate	300 ml
4	Polytrin C	Profenofos+Cypermethrin	350 ml
5	Castor oil	Ricin	350 ml
6	Neem oil	Azadirachtin	350 ml
7	Garlic oil	Allicin	300 ml
8	Jatropha oil	Curcin	300 ml

All the other standard agronomic practices were followed to get the healthy crop.

Insect infestation data

Five cotton plants were selected randomly from every treatment plot and mean percent infestation

data of *E. insulana* and *H. armigera* was calculated by Hajatmand *et al.* (2015) as under;

$$\text{Insect infestation (\%)} = \frac{\text{Damaged bolls/plant}}{\text{Total healthy bolls/plant}} \times 100$$

In case of *P. gossypiella* mean percent infestation was calculated by following formula.

$$\text{Insect infestation (\%)} = \frac{\text{Rosett flowers or bolls /plant}}{\text{Total healthy flowers or bolls/plant}} \times 100$$

Toxicity bioassays

Seeds of Neem, Jatropha, Castor-bean and G₁-garlic were purchased from a reliable source and dried under shade. Extraction of plant oils was done through Soxhlet extraction apparatus using solvent (De castro and Priego-Capote, 2010). Toxicity bioassays were performed at 10, 20 and 30% dilutions of each of the extracted plant oil against the three insect species. Synthetic insecticides; Profenofos (Curacon), Lambda-cyhalothrin (Karrate), Profenofos+Cypermethrin (Polo) and Emamectin-Benzoate (Proclaim) were purchased from Syngenta company sale point

located in Okara and were applied through Knapsack sprayer at recommended dose rates against *H. armigera*, *E. Insulana* and *P. gossypiella*. Experiments were conducted under Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD). Each treatment and control were replicated in thrice. Mortality data of the target insect pest were recorded after 24, 48, 72 and 96 h. of the spraying activity. Mean insect infestation data were recorded after regular intervals from 5 arbitrarily nominated plants from every experimental plot.

Crop Water Productivity

Crop Water productivity of the cotton was calculated according to formula given by Awan *et al.* (2007);

$$\text{Crop Water Productivity (Kg/m}^3\text{)} = \frac{\text{Lint Yield (Kg/ha)}}{\text{Amount of water applied (m}^3\text{/ha)}}$$

Statistical analysis

The collected data were analyzed through Statistic Software 8.1 and Means of treatments were separated by LSD (Gomez and Gomez, 1984).

Results

The main effects (insecticides and exposure periods) were statistically highly significant ($p < 0.01$) regarding mean number of infested bolls under different entomocidal chemicals exposure periods in case of two cotton genotypes; BS-15 and CKC-3, planting distances; 30 and 40 cm,

irrigation arrangements; single lateral and double laterals. Nevertheless, exposure period effects were found statistically non-significant in case of *Helicoverpa armigera* on CKC-3 plot under 40 cm planting distance and double lateral arrangements.

Table 2 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for mean infested bolls/flowers under different planting different insecticides, planting spaces, cotton genotypes and irrigation arrangements

Cotton bollworms	S.O.V	DF	BS-15				CKC-3			
			Single lateral		Double lateral		Single lateral		Double lateral	
			30 cm		40 cm		30 cm		40 cm	
			F (Cal.)	P-value						
<i>Helicoverpa armigera</i>	Blocks	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Treatments	7	712.56	P<0.01	867.10	P<0.01	546.19	P<0.05	734.90	P<0.01
	Exposure periods	3	4.39	P<0.01	6.89	P<0.01	4.39	P<0.01	2.61	P>0.05
	Treatments * Exposure periods	21	4.06	P<0.01	4.76	P<0.01	4.06	P<0.01	3.83	P<0.05
<i>Erias insulana</i>	Blocks	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Treatments	7	698.45	P<0.01	1041.22	P<0.01	532.89	P<0.05	972.13	P<0.01
	Exposure periods	3	8.52	P<0.01	5.17	P<0.01	12.07	P<0.01	8.86	P<0.01
	Treatments * Exposure periods	21	3.15	P<0.05	4.29	P<0.01	9.21	P<0.01	3.39	P<0.05
<i>Pectinophora gossypiella</i>	Blocks	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	Treatments	7	884.47	P<0.01	623.57	P<0.01	476.25	P<0.05	1057.20	P<0.01
	Exposure periods	3	5.34	P<0.01	6.89	P<0.01	6.90	P<0.01	7.69	P<0.01
	Treatments * Exposure periods	21	3.12	P<0.05	3.73	P<0.05	3.43	P<0.05	5.43	P<0.01

Outcomes (table 2) revealed that variations in mean values of mean infested bolls under different treatments arrangement were statistically significant (p<0.01). Control proved the least operative as relatively greater values of infested bolls per plant corresponding to each treatment. In case of treatments plots, maximum infested cotton bolls (2.01 mean infested bolls per plant) by *H. armigera* infestation were recorded in case of Jatropha oil under single lateral at 30 cm planting space in BS-15 variety of cotton while the lowest

(0.49 mean infested bolls per plant) were counted in case of Profenofos+Cypermethrin under single lateral at 40 cm in the same cotton genotype. The values were 1.45-1.89, 1.37-1.77, 1.76-1.93 and 1.58-2.01 mean infested bolls in case of Castor oil, neem oil, garlic oil, and jatropha oil, respectively. On other hand, the values were 0.89-1.34, 0.61-1.10, 0.74-1.52, 0.89-1.34 and 0.49-1.45 in case of profenofos, Lamdacyhalotrhin, Emamectinbenzoate, and Profenofos+Cypermethrin sprayed plot, respectively. In case of CKC-3, again control

proved the least effective as relatively greater values of infested bolls per plant at flood plots corresponding to each treatment. Maximum infested cotton bolls (1.90 mean infested bolls per plant) were enumerated in case of garlic oil under double lateral at 30 cm planting space whereas the minimum (0.21 mean infested bolls per plant) was computed in case of Profenofos+Cypermethrin under single lateral at 40 cm in the same cotton genotype. The values were 1.11-1.34, 1.47-1.81, 1.40-1.78 and 1.61-1.90 mean infested bolls in case of Castor oil, neem oil, jatropha oil and garlic oil, respectively. On other hand, the values were 0.57-1.18, 0.40-0.76, 0.53-0.85 and 0.21-0.45 in case of Profenofos, Lamdacyhalotrhin, Emamectin-benzoate, and Profenofos+Cypermethrin sprayed plot, respectively.

Results (table 3) discovered that variations in mean values of mean infested bolls under different treatments arrangement were statistically significant ($p < 0.01$). Relatively greater values of infested bolls per plant in flood plots corresponding to each treatment. In case of treatments plots, maximum infested cotton bolls (3.21 mean infested bolls per plant) by *E. insulana* infestation were noted in case of garlic oil under double lateral at 30 cm planting space in BS-15 variety of cotton whereas the minimum (0.54 mean infested bolls per plant) were recorded in case of Lamdacyhalotrhin under single lateral at 40 cm. The values were 1.98-2.43, 2.19-2.60, 2.89-3.21 and 2.24-2.56 mean infested bolls in case of Castor oil, neem oil, garlic oil, and jatropha oil, respectively. On other hand, the values were 0.92-1.47, 0.54-1.00, 0.81-2.29 and 0.45-1.34 in case of Profenofos, Lamdacyhalotrhin, Emamectin-benzoate, and Profenofos+Cypermethrin sprayed plot, respectively. In case of CKC-3, again control proved the least effective as relatively greater values of infested bolls per plant at flood plots corresponding to each treatment. Maximum infested cotton bolls (2.92 mean infested bolls per plant) were enumerated in case of garlic oil under double lateral at 30 cm planting space whereas the minimum (0.39 mean infested bolls per plant) was computed in case of Lamdacyhalotrhin under single lateral at 40 cm in the same cotton genotype.

The values were 1.92-2.37, 2.10-2.53, 2.49-2.92 and 2.21-2.59 mean infested bolls in case of Castor oil, neem oil, garlic oil and jatropha oil, respectively. On other hand, the values were 0.65-1.23, 0.39-0.68, 0.69-0.92 and 0.47-0.75 in case of Profenofos, Lamdacyhalotrhin, Emamectin-benzoate, and Profenofos+Cypermethrin sprayed plot, respectively.

Findings (table 4) disclosed that fluctuations in mean values of mean infested bolls under different treatments arrangement were statistically significant ($p < 0.01$). Relatively greater values of infested bolls per plant in flood plots corresponding to each treatment. In case of treatments plots, maximum infested cotton bolls (3.23 mean infested bolls per plant) by *P. gossypiella* infestation were noted in case of garlic oil under double lateral at 40 cm planting space in BS-15 variety of cotton while the minimum (0.58 mean infested bolls per plant) were recorded in case of Profenofos+Cypermethrin under single lateral at 40 cm. The values were 2.38-2.89, 2.16-2.89, 2.49-3.23 and 2.64-2.95 mean infested bolls in case of Castor oil, neem oil, garlic oil and jatropha oil, correspondingly. On other hand, the values were 0.69-1.43, 0.95-1.12, 2.23-2.78 and 0.58-0.98 in case of Profenofos, Lamdacyhalotrhin, Emamectin-benzoate, and Profenofos+Cypermethrin sprayed plot, respectively. In case of CKC-3, control proved the least operative as relatively greater values of infested bolls per plant at flood plots corresponding to each treatment. Maximum infested cotton bolls (2.92 mean infested bolls per plant) were enumerated in case of garlic oil under double lateral at 30 cm planting space while the minimum (0.37 mean infested bolls per plant) was computed in case of Profenofos+Cypermethrin under single lateral at 40 cm in the same cotton genotype. The values were 1.64-1.98, 1.79-2.17, 2.10-2.45 and 2.29-2.79 mean infested bolls in case of Castor oil, neem oil, garlic oil and jatropha oil, individually. On other hand, the values were 0.51-1.00, 0.56-0.89, 2.10-2.69 and 0.37-0.76 in case of Profenofos, Lamdacyhalotrhin, Emamectin-benzoate, and Profenofos+Cypermethrin sprayed plot, respectively.

Table 2 showed the mean number of infested bolls by *Helicoverpa armigera* on two cotton genotypes under different treatment applications and planting geometries during study period

Variety	Treat.	Planting space			
		30 cm		40 cm	
		Single lateral	Double lateral	Single lateral	Double lateral
BS-15	Pofenophos	0.95±0.10c	1.34±0.5bc	0.89±0.21bc	1.23±0.54hi
	Lamda-cyhalothrin	0.68±0.19cd	1.10±0.81bcd	0.61±0.21bcd	0.96±0.81d
	Emamectin-Benzoate	0.93±0.10c	1.52±0.71bc	0.74±0.14bcd	1.19±0.71bcd
	Profenofos+Cyperm ethrin	0.55±0.12cd	1.45±0.59bc	0.49±0.12cd	1.28±0.59bcd
	C	2.48±0.67a	2.61±0.89ab	2.43±0.83ab	2.39±0.89ab
	Castor oil	1.53±0.43ab	1.89±0.56ef	1.45±0.43bc	1.73±0.56bc
	Neem oil	1.68±0.52ab	1.77±0.67b	1.37±0.61bc	1.61±0.67bc
	Garlic oil	1.89±0.49ab	1.93±0.82b	1.76±0.43b	1.82±0.82bc
	Jatropha oil	2.01±0.24ab	1.81±0.60b	1.67±0.39b	1.58±0.27b
	C	3.29±0.91a	3.45±1.10a	3.53±1.11a	3.21±1.10a
	CKC-3	Pofenophos	0.75±0.12cd	1.18±0.41bcd	0.57±0.10bcd
Lamda-cyhalothrin		0.48±0.16de	0.76±0.21d	0.40±0.18cd	0.70±0.21d
Emamectin-Benzoate		0.64±0.10bcd	0.85±0.15d	0.53±0.15cd	0.78±0.15d
Profenofos+Cyperm ethrin		0.31±0.10e	0.45±0.23e	0.21±0.12d	0.41±0.23e
C		2.29±0.39a	2.19±0.98ab	2.18±0.55a	2.10±0.98ab
Castor oil		1.26±0.52abc	1.34±0.83bc	1.11±0.79bc	1.17±0.83bcd
Neem oil		1.62±0.46 ab	1.81±1.12b	1.47±0.46 bc	1.59±1.12b
Garlic oil		1.52±0.11ab	1.78±0.94b	1.40±0.77b	1.65±0.44b
Jatropha oil		1.78±0.61ab	1.90±1.00b	1.61±0.92b	1.88±1.00b
C		2.95±0.83a	3.12±1.14a	2.78±0.61a	3.00±1.14a

Where, T= Treatments, Pofenophos, Lamda-cyhalothrin, Emamectin-Benzoate, Profenofos + Cypermethrin, Castor oil, Neem oil, Garlic oil, Jatropha oil and C= Control.

Treatments means sharing similar lettering within a row are statistically not different from each other.

Table 3 showed the mean number of infested bolls by *Earias insulana* on two cotton genotypes under different treatment applications and planting geometries during study period

Variety	Treat.	Planting space			
		30 cm		40 cm	
		Single lateral	Double lateral	Single lateral	Double lateral
BS-15	Pofenophos	1.08±0.71bc	1.47±0.88bcd	0.92±0.41d	1.12±0.65c
	Lamda-cyhalothrin	0.65±0.03cd	1.00±0.23bcd	0.54±0.25d	0.87±0.32cd
	Emamectin-Benzoate	1.97±0.43b	2.29±0.79bc	0.81±0.14d	2.14±0.29ab
	Profenofos+Cypermet hrin	0.78±0.24bc	1.34±0.46bc	0.45±0.21de	1.00±0.13c
	C	3.21±0.92ab	3.41±1.10ab	2.98±0.29b	3.45±1.05a
	Castor oil	2.25±1.00b	2.43±0.92bc	1.98±0.71c	2.31±0.85ab
	Neem oil	2.51±0.92b	2.60±1.10b	2.19±0.67bc	2.49±0.92ab
	Garlic oil	3.12±0.57ab	3.21±1.00ab	2.89±0.25b	3.00±1.00ab
	Jatropha oil	2.47±0.64b	2.56±0.89b	2.24±0.78bc	2.43±0.61ab
	C	4.78±1.12a	5.10±1.52a	4.61±1.10a	4.76±1.24a
	CKC-3	Pofenophos	0.74±0.11bcd	1.23±0.bc	0.65±0.13d
Lamda-cyhalothrin		0.47±0.09d	0.68±0.09d	0.39±0.17e	0.61±0.11d
Emamectin-Benzoate		0.78±0.14bc	0.92±0.14cd	0.69±0.10d	0.83±0.10c
Profenofos+Cypermet hrin		0.51±0.10d	0.75±0.10cd	0.47±0.12de	0.71±0.14c
C		2.89±0.77b	3.10±0.77ab	2.78±0.77b	2.92±0.77ab
Castor oil		2.13±0.41bbc	2.37±0.41bc	1.92±0.41c	2.18±0.41abc
Neem oil		2.47±0.41b	2.53±0.41b	2.10±0.41bc	2.29±0.41ab
Garlic oil		2.86±0.41b	2.92±0.41b	2.49±0.41abc	2.66±0.41ab
Jatropha oil		2.38±0.41bc	2.59±0.41b	2.21±0.41bc	2.43±0.41ab
C		4.56±1.12a	4.70±1.82a	4.56±1.10a	4.39±1.36a

Table 4 showed the mean infestation reduction by *Pectinophora gossypiella* on two cotton genotypes under different treatment applications and plant geometries

Variety	Treat.	Planting space			
		30 cm		40 cm	
		Single lateral	Double lateral	Single lateral	Double lateral
BS-15	Pofenophos	0.78±0.12c	1.43±0.54bcd	0.69±0.17d	1.32±0.20
	Lamda-cyhalothrin	0.95±0.17c	1.12±0.43cd	0.73±0.10d	1.00±0.16de
	Emamectin-Benzoate	2.56±0.10b	2.78±0.67ab	2.23±0.19bc	2.53±0.37ab
	Profenofos+Cypermethrin	0.61±0.13cd	0.98±0.21	0.58±0.10d	0.87±0.14de
	C	4.07±1.12a	4.22±1.12a	4.00±1.21ab	4.10±1.39a
	Castor oil	2.38±0.68b	2.77±0.35ab	2.38±0.68bc	2.89±0.23ab
	Neem oil	2.16±0.56	2.89±0.56ab	2.16±0.56bcd	2.76±0.12ab
	Garlic oil	2.49±0.43b	3.10±1.10ab	2.49±0.43bc	3.23±1.00ab
	Jaropha oil	2.81±0.51b	2.95±0.92ab	2.81±0.51bc	2.64±0.40ab
	C	4.33±1.11a	4.56±1.41a	4.33±1.11a	4.45±1.76a
	CKC-3	Pofenophos	0.65±0.12cd	1.00±0.34cd	0.51±0.22de
Lamda-cyhalothrin		0.80±0.34c	0.89±0.21d	0.63±0.11de	0.56±0.11e
Emamectin-Benzoate		2.41±0.96ab	2.69±0.42bc	2.10±0.72bcd	2.45±0.3bc
Profenofos+Cypermethrin		0.48±0.11d	0.76±0.10	0.37±0.10e	0.70±0.18e
C		3.90±1.12ab	4.26±1.92a	3.77±1.10b	4.10±1.67a
Castor oil		1.92±0.13bc	1.98±0.12c	1.83±0.19cd	1.64±0.21bcd
Neem oil		2.08±0.61bc	2.17±0.43bc	1.79±0.28cd	1.88±0.72bcd
Garlic oil		2.33±0.45b	2.45±0.28bc	2.18±0.15bcd	2.10±0.18bc
Jatropha oil		2.60±0.21b	2.79±0.32bc	2.48±0.11bc	2.29±0.11bc
C		4.48±1.43a	4.61±1.43a	4.35±1.54a	4.38±1.23a

Crop Water Productivity (CWP)

Data (fig. 1) showed that comparatively greater values of crop water productivity were recorded in cotton experimental plots under drip irrigation compared with flood irrigated plots. Maximum CWP (0.19 kgm⁻³) was computed in case of CKC-

3 with planting distance of 40 cm under drip irrigation compared with corresponding control plot while the minimum (0.10 kgm⁻³) in case of flood irrigated plot of BS -15 variety of cotton with planting distance of 30 cm.

Results (Table 4.11) showed that CWP was greater (0.61 kg/m³) in case of experimental plots under drip irrigation system compared with the experimental plot under surface irrigation (0.53 0.61 kg/m³).

Table 4.11 Comparison of crop water productivity of cotton under two irrigation regimes

Experimental plot	Water applied (mm)	Yield (kg)	CWP (Kg/m ³)
Control plot (under surface irrigation)	345	184	0.53
Experimental plot (under drip irrigation system)	290	180	0.61

Discussion

Lepidopterous pests including *H. armigera*, *E. insulana* and *P. gossypiella* have been known to cause cotton crop infestations in African and Indo-Pakistan areas. Toxic synthetic pesticides are used to manage these economically significant bugs (Balmala *et al.*, 2023). However, as previously mentioned, the careless and unreasonable use of artificial chemicals has resulted in a number of environmental problems. In order to better incorporate these botanical and conventional extracts into various biorational pest control strategies, this study set out to screen them out against cotton bollworms in a field setting. Results of study in case of *H. armigera* infestation showed that maximum infested cotton bolls (2.01 mean

infested bolls per plant) were logged in case of Jatropha oil under single lateral at 30 cm planting space in BS-15 variety of cotton whereas the minimum (0.49 mean infested bolls per plant) were counted in case of Profenofos+Cypermethrin under single lateral at 40 cm in the same cotton genotype. However, comparatively less infested bolls were enumerated in case of CKC-3 variety of cotton. The highest infested cotton bolls (3.21 mean infested bolls per plant) in case of *E. insulana* infestation were observed in case of garlic oil under double lateral at 30 cm planting space in BS-15 variety of cotton whereas the lowest (0.54 mean infested bolls per plant) were recorded in case of Lamdacyhalotrhin under single lateral at 40 cm. Crop Water Productivity showed that

comparatively greater values of crop water productivity were recorded in cotton experimental plots under drip irrigation compared with flood irrigated plots. Many researchers have studied the chewing insect pests of bollworms on cotton crops. Numerous lepidopterous insect pests have been demonstrated to be effectively controlled by this insecticide, such as the cabbage looper (*P. xylostella*) (Liu *et al.*, 2002), the tomato fruit borer (Ravi *et al.*, 2008), the gram pod borer (Babariya *et al.*, 2010) and codling moths (Loriatti *et al.*, 2009). Numerous research trials have demonstrated the effectiveness of *A. indica* extract against a variety of insect pests, such as the cabbage diamondback moth (*P. xylostella*), *Spodoptera exigua*, *Sesamia calamistis*, okra fruit and shoot borer (*E. vittella*), and brinjal fruit and shoot borer (*Leucinodes orbonalis*) (Akhtar *et al.*, 2019). *N. tabacum* was the second-maximum operative botanical extract in this investigation, reducing fruit infection up to the seventh day after treatment and increasing okra fruit production. Different research investigations have shown that extract of tobacco leaves may effectively control okra insect pests and other plants. Unfortunately, the majority of plant-derived chemicals were effective for very brief periods of time. The brief effectiveness of botanicals against insect pests may be due, in part, to the unprocessed and unrefined character of aqueous extracts as opposed to pure extractives. *P. gossypiella*, often known as the pink bollworm, is a serious pest of cotton crops that primarily affects fruiting bodies and causes significant losses in cotton production, especially lint quality (Peddu *et al.*, 2020). Since the pink bollworm is an interior eater, controlling it effectively depends greatly on when to apply insecticides. This is due to the fact that the pest spends its whole larval stage within the bolls, at which point the pesticide application loses its effectiveness. There is a relatively little window of 7-8 days after moth emergence begins for cotton producers to use pesticide treatments in order to effectively manage pink bollworm (Fand *et al.*, 2021). While the introduction of Bt cotton types has demonstrated notable resistance against the bollworm complex, the discovery of *P.*

gossypiella's resistance to Bt cotton has presented cotton producers with additional difficulties.

Crop water productivity (CWP) is a term used to determine the way water is used in agricultural systems for crop production. It measures the correlation between the amount of water used for irrigation or rainfall and the yield of crops that results (Moursy *et al.*, 2023). Since it aids in evaluating the efficacy and sustainability of agricultural practices as well as their effects on water resources, CWP is a crucial topic in agriculture and water resource management (Cheng *et al.*, 2023). In present research work, comparatively less water was applied in case of drip irrigation compared with flood irrigated plots. Maximum crop-water productivity was recorded in case of golden with low dense planting. Results of increased crop water productivity of drip irrigated plot were corroborated by findings of Manjunath *et al.* (2019) who also recorded superior values of crop water productivity under drip irrigation than flood irrigation.

Conclusion

From the results, it could be inferred that botanicals possess entomocidal effects against the bollworms of the cotton. Repeated use of the synthetic insecticides has resulted in environmental pollution and resistance development in cotton bollworms. Tripple gene genotype of cotton and botanicals could be effective agents in the Integrated Pest Management program (IPM) of the cotton bollworms, leading to mitigate the environmental pollution and resistance problems.

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